

ABSTRACT

Computational tool for epitope prediction in *Trypanosoma cruzi* antigens based on phage display data

Silva, G. M. M.^{1,2}; Giordano, R. J.²; Setubal, J. C.^{1,2}.

¹Interunit Graduate Program in Bioinformatics, University of São Paulo, São Paulo, Brazil; ²Department of Biochemistry, Institute of Chemistry, University of São Paulo, São Paulo, Brazil.

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The epitopes of antigenic (protein) sequences are small sections of these proteins (usually between 10 and 30 aa). These are the sections that bind to antibodies. Knowing them and the proteins to which they belong is fundamental for the development of vaccines, diagnostic tests and other therapeutic options for infectious and parasitic diseases such as Chagas disease caused by *Trypanosoma cruzi*. In this work, we present the initial steps in developing a computational tool for predicting epitopes in *T. cruzi* antigens based on phage display data. Phage display (PD) involves the insertion of a DNA fragment into a bacteriophage (phage) surface coat protein gene, allowing the corresponding peptide encoded by the exogenous DNA fragment to be displayed on the phage surface. If this peptide is a fragment of an antigen recognized by a specific antibody present in the solution, the phage particle binds to the antibody, enabling its capture and isolation from the pool of phage particles. Our methodology comprises several stages: after pre-processing, we map PD fragments in the *T. cruzi* genome and identify all mapped segments, specifying their start and end positions. Subsequently, we employ multiple sequence alignment (MSA) on the peptides clustered within each segment to identify conserved regions and generate a consensus sequence. Following this, we conduct a quality control check on each set of results to assess if there are known epitopes matching the consensus sequences. Finally, we associate the epitopes with their respective antigens, using *T. cruzi* epitope data from the IEDB database for quality control. This methodology has been applied to the PD dataset from Teixeira et al. (2021), encompassing datasets from four groups of Chagas disease patients, with two cohorts (A and B) for each dataset, totaling 5,599,446 unprocessed PD sequences. In the mapping process, we identified 29,975 segments, with 28,589 and 1,386 segments from cohort A and B, respectively. A subset of segments was selected to evaluate the MSA and consensus sequence identification process, demonstrating high agreement with epitopes cataloged in the IEDB database. Currently, we are applying MSA to all mapped segments and evaluating the results. Additionally, we are concurrently working on identifying potential quality filters that could enhance the process.

Keywords: Epitopes; Antigenic; Phage Display; *Trypanosoma cruzi*; Computational Tools; Prediction.

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